

Promoting Human Values through High School Curriculum: A Study into Discourse Features of Pakistani ELT Textbooks

Sajid Waqar, Zarnab Ahmed, Sania Jabeen

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 03, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Textbook Evaluation, English Curriculum, Elt Syllabus, Human Values, Cda, Readership Conceptions</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4912254</p>	<p><i>This study focuses on textbooks' embedded themes about human values in secondary level ELT textbooks of Pakistan, namely Baluchistan Textbook Board (BTB) Quetta, Sindh Textbook Board (STB) Jamshoro, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Textbook Board (KTB) Peshawar and Punjab Textbook Board (PTB) Lahore. To accomplish the objectives, the study is delineated into two distinct parts: in part one human values related textbook contents have been identified and analyzed by using Fairclough's (1995) three-dimensional framework augmented by Van Dijk's (2006) socio-cognitive approach. The second part of the study is dedicated to obtaining readership's conceptions related to human values through questionnaire-based survey all over the country. The study reveals an adequate inclusion of human-values related themes in all four ELT textbooks. The findings of part 2 indicate that human values related to tolerance and equality are adequately present in readership's minds. In contrast, virtues such as honesty and patience are found lacking among young males and females. The research recommends a human values-based test of all textbooks at the national level before publication to ensure improved human values related contents in the syllabus as directed in National Curriculum of Pakistan.</i></p>

Introduction

The famous Chinese spiritual leader Dalai Lama says, 'In order to lead a meaningful life, you need to cherish others, pay attention to human values, and *cultivate inner peace*.' All theologies of the world have advocated human values. The religion of Islam lays great emphasis on teachings and practices of human values. Pakistan is the Islamic Republic where over 95% of the population is Muslim, and Islam is the State religion as per its constitution. English is the medium of instruction and enjoys second language (L2) status in the country. There is a central government and four provincial governments in the country where ministries of education work at both the centre and provinces. Educational and English language curricula are formulated by the education ministry of the federal government seated at the capital city of Islamabad. As the country is a federation, the provinces have their respective education ministries and textbook boards that publish English Language Teaching textbooks while keeping the contents aligned with the National Curriculum for English Language (NCEL) 2006, Ministry of Education, Pakistan. The competency focused in this Paper is '*appropriate ethical and social development*' through the four provincial textbook boards' English textbooks at High School level (grade IX and X). The curriculum advises foregrounding ethical or human values in the discourse of textbooks - otherwise meant to target various language learning skills. Human Values are the positive, desirable qualities of character such as honesty, integrity, tolerance, responsibility, compassion, altruism, justice and respect inherent in all human beings (Prabhu 2011). It is very pertinent to mention that at present, '*National Curriculum-2006*' has been fully implemented by the Federal Government of Pakistan. Specific themes such as bravery, honesty, fair play, truthfulness, friendship, tolerance, justice, patience, humanism, respect for elders, social adjustment, peaceful co-existence, and gender equality have been suggested as guidelines to provincial textbook developers in ELT textbooks. Human values such as cooperation, respect and tolerance affect public's private perceptions, judgments, motivations and actions toward others in diverse circumstances in changing cultures, societies and religions (Baba, 2011 quoted in Rass, 2014). Henceforth, the umbrella term 'human values' will be used for the suggested themes. The past research studies focusing on embedded cultural and humanism themes and various ideologies in ELT textbooks have found varied results.

Milton (1644) considered books superior to humans as books were termed immortal where humans were mortal. The reading of Pakistani secondary level ELT textbooks reveals that local writers and developers write mostly the lessons. So, the textbooks are replete with local cultural themes, ideologies and explicit teachings for the learners. However, elite private schools in Pakistan follow "Oxford Progressive English" (OPE), loaded with Western cultural values. Shah and Ahmad (2014) brought out that '*Oxford Progressive English*' (OPE) imparted foreign colonial agenda in the guise of the hidden curriculum, which was a great hindrance in learning English. Chao (2011) found that the '*New American Inside Out*' series taught in Taiwan were replete with target

USA cultural contents. The process of teaching and learning should be formed in a happy and different situation (Ariyanti, 2016).

The present study contends that Pakistani ELT textbooks at the secondary level published by the State are replete with moral and human values instead of Western cultural contents. The researcher carried out a detailed study of the present National Curriculum 2006 and all the provincial ELT textbooks published by four provincial publishing textbook boards to validate the claim. The contents related to human values such as tolerance, patience, equality, justice, truth, honesty were deconstructed from textbooks' discourse by employing Fairclough's (1995) three-dimensional framework combined with (Van Dijk 2006). Textbooks are an effective tool for imparting different ideologies in readers' minds (Yaqoob 2011). To make this study a vital contributor to the existing scholarship on the subject, a countrywide survey was also conducted while relying on a closed-ended- questionnaire based on Likert Five-point attitudinal scales. The study in hand is unique in that it targets the ELT text books published by all the country's state-sponsored text boards. Moreover, the research focuses on ethical conceptions of the readership of all geographical areas of Pakistan.

1.1 Research Questions

The study relied on the following research questions:

- 1) How are secondary level ELT textbooks' contents of Pakistan embedded with human values teachings?
- 2) What are general conceptions of ELT textbooks readership about human values?
- 3) To what extent ELT textbooks' human values- related contents are aligned with human values-directed in National for Curriculum English Language (NCEL) 2006?

Literature Review

Rass (2014) reported the findings of a study conducted to examine the success and feasibility of integrating human values in EFL syllabi in a teacher training college of Israel. The project aimed to blend human values such as tolerance, respect and cooperation in a troubled society of the country. The project adopted content-based teaching and problem-solving approach were folktales, video segments and group discussions encompassed all language skills.

Srinivasulu(2018) was focused on human values such as truth, happiness, justice, freedom, equality, love, security and peace of mind inculcated in university students' minds. The study project carried out a sort of experiment by making the respondents study literary plays for five weeks. The post test results of the students who studied literature were compared with freshmen students of the same department of an Indian University. However, no difference was observed in the conceptions of two respondents in Kolbian categorization.

Maghsoudi (2020) evaluated the course books written by local writers, namely, the Prospect, and English Standard being taught in Iran and India. The textbooks' contents were analysed and deconstructed by carrying out critical discourse analysis (CDA) using Van Dijk's (1998, 2001) socio-cognitive model and framework provided by (Kress and Van Leeuwen's 1996) multi-functional model. The integrated framework investigated both the textual and meta-textual aspects of the textbooks. The study results indicated that intercultural values were ignored in the textbooks, and 'Self' was invested while ignoring 'otherness'.

Baig et al. (2020) aimed to review and evaluate the "appropriate ethical and social development" incorporated in the National Curriculum for English Language (NCEL) 2006, Ministry of Education Pakistan. The elementary level ELT textbook was selected as study material that had been directed to embed appropriate ethical and social development by the State. The study results discovered that the textbook covered the themes of tolerance and humanism. However, the intended learner outcomes to develop students' moral and social aptitudes were ignored; nonetheless, both aspects were deemed essential in a multicultural and civilised society.

Research Methodology

In the light of various research dimensions proposed by Kumar, Dornyei and Creswell and narrated in preceding paragraphs, the present research can be termed as descriptive, qualitative with quantitative and statistical measurements. According to Dornyei (2007), this research can be labelled as, mixed-method approach. According to Brown (2003), a qualitative study can breed new hypothesis. Primarily, this research is qualitative in nature but supplemented by quantitative data. The study was conducted in two phases. The study aimed to gauge humanistic values of class 10th students of all the provinces of Pakistan. To make the study results more and more valid, cluster and random sampling were adopted wherein male and female students; rural and urban areas of all the provinces were covered while administering a questionnaire-based survey. The districts of respective provinces that were selected for attitudinal questionnaire-based survey. About 70% of the total study population follows Punjab Textbook Board (PTB) Lahore syllabus. PTB Lahore textbooks are taught in Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK), Gilgit Baltistan and Federal Government (FG) schools located in Federal Territory and all the provinces of Pakistan. Accordingly, more number of students and teachers were selected for Phase 2 of the research. Due to some administrative and security constraints, it could not be possible to select the respondents in ratio with their actual population in different Pakistan provinces.

Framework of Analysis

Fairclough's three-dimensional models of critical discourse analysis (1995) and van Dijk's socio-cultural approach (2006) were used as major analytical tool for effectively deconstructing embedded themes in a stretch

of textbooks' discourse. In the next section, its brief account will be provided. It is imperative to appreciate the cognitive processes behind language use and comprehension, which are part of the discourse practice, to unearth ideologically biased discourse (van Dijk, 2006). Language use depends on, and simultaneously influences, how individuals interpret its content and how they perceive the communicative situation (Lombardi 2013).

Study Material Population and Sample

The material of the present study comprised of all secondary level ELT textbooks followed in State-run schools of Pakistan. Baluchistan Textbook Board (BTB) Quetta follows 'A TEXTBOOK OF ENGLISH Language Grade 9' and 'A Text Book of ENGLISH for Class X'; Sindh Textbook Board (STB) Jamshoro follows 'SECONDARY STAGE ENGLISH BOOK ONE FOR CLASS IX' and 'Secondary Stage English Book Two For Class X'; Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) Textbook Board (KTB) Peshawar follows 'Textbook of ENGLISH Grade – IX' and 'English Reading Book For Class 10' and Punjab Textbook Board (PTB) Lahore follows 'ENGLISH 9' and 'ENGLISH 10' books for teaching of English subject to secondary level students of State-run Schools. Nonetheless, the representative text or sample was extracted from the text books' discourse for text analysis.

Both the male and female students between 15-18 years of age from rural and urban areas of Pakistan formed the study population of the survey conducted in phase 2 of the study to gather readership conceptions related to human values. The survey relied on close-ended questionnaire for smooth quantification of data using AlTamimi and Shuib (2009) questionnaire model. However, instead of exclusively relying on random sampling, cluster sampling and random sampling techniques were employed while depending upon the researcher's knowledge about the socio-cultural features of Pakistani society.

Research Site

For the quest of present research, all the provinces and territories of Pakistan i.e., Baluchistan, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK) and Gilgit Baltistan (GB) areas were selected as site of the study.

Key Terms and Categories for Analysis

The analytical terms such as assumption, presupposition, Implicature, metaphor, representations, intertextuality, dialogicality, difference, comparison, universalization, prominence, foregrounding, exclusion and back grounding were employed in text analysis in this study. Themes related to humanism, tolerance, patience, honesty, justice, equality, truth and peaceful mutual co-existence were focused in this study.

Limitations and Delimitations

The study has targeted only the syllabus of State-run schools, whereas other ELT textbooks taught in private schools have not been included in the research. The research could focus only on ELT textbooks of grade IX and X. However, remaining subjects and lower grade school classes have been kept outside the scope of study to stay focused on the research.

Data Analysis

During intensive pre-reading of ELT textbooks, the representative data extracted from textbooks' discourse is described in succeeding sub paragraphs.

Representative Text (sample data for analysis)

The text related to human values was extracted from the textbooks of four provincial publishing boards. For the convenience of analysis and easy comprehension of readership of this paper, the extracts from different publishing boards have been described under separate subparagraphs.

Data Analysis based on Fairclough (1995) and Van Dijk's Sociocognitive Approach (2006)

For simplicity and efficient handling of the vast data, the researchers resorted to a top-down approach rather than the bottom-up method in using three dimensional framework of analysis provided by Fairclough (1995) in the following subsections of this research.

Socio-cultural Practice- Place of Human Values in Pakistan

Pakistan is the Islamic Republic as per its constitution of 1973. It claims to be an ideological state, as the basis of its creation in 1947 was the religion of Islam. The first legislative assembly of the country passed the famous 'Objectives Resolution' that declared the pro-Islamic complexion of its future constitution. Islam was adopted as State religion in first constitution of Pakistan in 1956. A vast majority of population in Pakistan is Muslim. The religion of Islam gives much importance to human values such as peace, tolerance, patience. In a conservative society of Pakistan, female gender has a comparatively limited and peculiar social role due to socio cultural and religious reasons. The religion of Islam also advocates the ethics related values such as honesty, justice, equality, tolerance, humanism and patience. The Islamic role models have been represented to practice such virtues of ethics to their best. While carrying out the analysis of socio-cultural practice of a communicative event, the researcher should explore different layers such as the immediate situational context, the context of institutional practices the event is enclosed in, or the broader frame of society and culture (Fairclough 1995). Accordingly, the socio cultural context in Pakistan has been described briefly.

Pakistan has four provinces, Federal Areas and a disputed State of AJK & GB. The socio cultural environments of all the areas differ from each other. However, history indicates that the relations with ethical values of the country are pretty ambivalent. No significant variation within provinces as regards to culture and ethics exists. It is through the lenses of this socio-cultural context that the text analysis of the sampled textbooks' extracts or representative data will be conducted. The immediate social and historical contexts will be described along with respective extract's analysis.

Discourse Practice – Textbooks Development and Teaching/Learning in Pakistan

In Pakistan, the State organs have frequently manipulated the textbooks' discourse and included the themes and ideologies to achieve specific vested interests. The textbooks equate Pakistan with Islam, militarism with Jihad, military with Mujahedeen and the Pakistanis with the Muslims (Nayyar & Saleem 2003). This section investigates the procedures adopted in the curriculum policy of Federal Government of Pakistan, publication policies of the provincial textbook boards, printing and distribution of textbooks and finally, their worthiness and learning outcomes. It has already been mentioned above that the publishing boards selected for this study are BTB Quetta, STB Jamshoro, KTB Peshawar and PTB Lahore. The textbooks' substances of four provincial textbook boards are mutually different. However, all the textbook boards follow the publication policy of central government of Pakistan as directed in National English Language Curriculum 2006. Accordingly, the contents pertaining to human values do not indicate significant disparities among the four publishing boards' ELT textbooks. The provincial textbook boards keep revising textbook substances periodically to improve student learners' learning outcomes. In ELT textbooks, some themes are embedded to instill certain values in students' minds. Social conditioning through schooling is the most important way of changing worldview whether taken by business organization or by the State (Galbraith 1984). Apple (2004 & 1993) regards curriculum, in any society or country, as a means to an unequal distribution of power and, then, to its legitimization with the minimum of conflict (Quoted in Yaqoob 2012). So, the text production in syllabus books is always value-laden, in a positive or negative sense.

Text Consumption- Teaching/Learning

This section offers an overview of how the ethics or human values related themes can be comprehended. Therefore, while analysing the values cognitively processed by the readership, relying upon van Dijk's (2006) socio-cognitive approach, this study does not presume to offer a comprehensive qualitative analysis, achievable only with the support of more empirical data and the use of a different research methods such as focus group discussions or interviews addressed to the various stakeholders like class teachers and textbook developers. For instance, to understand the cognitive processes behind the interpretation of the ELT contents, it is necessary to identify the average readership of the four sets of different ELT textbooks being analyzed. The average readership of secondary level textbooks is having age between 15-18 years. Both the female and male students read these same textbooks. The urban and rural readers of different provinces and areas such as Baluchistan, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab and AJK&GB follow the same national curriculum of Pakistan. Notwithstanding the variations among readership such as gender, age, social and cultural environments, the textbooks' contents can be understood differently according to different subjective mental models and context models. Depending on the readers' personal experiences and how these are represented in his or her Episodic memory, thus forming individual mental models, a textbook content or theme may be comprehended differently. It may be added that episodic memory is the memory of autobiographical events (times, places, associated emotions, and other contextual knowledge) that can be clearly stated or invented (Van Dijk 2006). Foregoing in view, a portion on readership's conceptions has been dedicated to getting empirical data through comprehensive questionnaire-based surveys, conducted in all the provinces of Pakistan. The responses on the questionnaire have been invited on five points Likert's attitudinal scales so that maximum allowance of variation in cognition and mental models of different respondents is well catered for. An effort has been made to study the mental models of readership through indirect questions on culture and ethics.

Textual Analysis

The text is analyzed linguistically in text dimension by looking at vocabulary, semantics, and sentence order (Fairclough, 1995). He also included coherence and cohesiveness: how between words or sentences combined to form understanding. Here, the analysis of selected extracts or representative data from ELT textbooks will be carried out. The text shall be analyzed while focusing on word choice, adjectives, phrases, sentence form and structure, signification in paragraph and transitivity etc. The way textbook writers construct different identities through lexical choices, connotative & denotative meaning of words, and figurative language will also be considered while analyzing selected extracts. The key terms such as otherness, metaphor, backgrounding and foregrounding, presupposition will also be used while deconstructing layered texts. In order to have a fair idea of lexicalization used by the textbook developers, the key words/ phrases have been tabulated below. The table provides a sort of quantitative data for analysis where the number of lessons and key words dedicated to the human values by the four publishing boards can be compared.

Table 1. Lesson titles and keywords in four textbook boards' textbooks

S.	Publishing	Lesson Title	Key Words/Phrases
----	------------	--------------	-------------------

No.	Board		
1	BTB Quetta	The Bird and the Elephant	Finally, he begged the bird to leave him alone and in return he promised that he would never again scratch his back against her tree.
		Nursing: A Noble Profession Cruelty to Animals	Commitment, sense of sacrifice, love for humanity, a great deal of tolerance kind , sympathetic, kind and thoughtful to men
2	STB Jamshoro	Eid-ul-Azha The last Sermon of the Holy Prophet Quaid-i-Azam and his Vision for Pakistan Nursing	our duty to the poor and needy, to live for others complete legal equality with men free to go to your temples, free to go to your Mosques, no discrimination no distinction between one community and another, all citizens of one State sympathy and love
3	KTB Peshawar	Dignity of Work The Medina Charter The Holy Prophet Hazrat Muhammad (SAW)	loved doing work for himself civic equality, freedom of worship, religions and racial tolerance kindness and affection, faithful
4	PTB Lahore	Hazrat Umar Farooq (RA) Faithfulness Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH) an Embodiment of Justice	impartial justice, kind and sympathetic, Honesty and integrity perfection in the moral, spiritual and social areas of life, honest, fair and just business man, justice and equity perfection in the moral, spiritual and social areas of life, honest, fair and just business man, merit , justice and equity, irrespective of color, creed, or race, justice, without fear of favor

In succeeding paragraphs, one extract from each publishing board's ELT textbook content will be analysed as the comprehensive textual analyses of all representative data are likely to stretch beyond the volume of the paper.

Textual Analysis of BTB Quetta Extract

Would you like to be praised for your knowledge or to be called a savage? Modern man is proud of being civilized and shows his civilized nature by being kind and sympathetic. If a person is cruel to animals, something human is missing in him. He is not likely to be kind and thoughtful to men. (BTB, X, Cruelty to Animals, page 26)

The extract is from the lesson titled 'Cruelty to Animals'. The author described different events of a village festival and focused on the sport of bear baiting. The sport was popular in Western world especially Elizabethan England. The author of the lesson has equated the term 'knowledge' with civilization and watching of the sport with 'savagery'. Through the tools of Implicature and entailment, civilization has in turn been equated with kindness and sympathy. The extract conveys a deeper message or lesson to the reader to be kind and to animals and sympathy. The discourse 'Implicature' has been wisely employed to educate the readership on human values of kindness and sympathy to fellow humans.

Textual Analysis of STB Jamshoro Extract

"You are free; you are free to go to your temples, you are free to go to your Mosques, or to any other place of worship in this State of Pakistan. You may belong to any religion or caste or creed that has nothing to do with the State's business. We are starting in the days when there is no discrimination no distinction between one community and another. We are starting with this fundamental principle that we are all citizens of one State... .. 'now, I think we should keep that in front of us as our ideal and you will find that in course of time Hindus would cease to be Hindus, and Muslims would cease to be Muslims, not in the religious sense because that is the personal faith of each individual, but in the political sense as the citizens of the state."

(STB, IX, Quaid-i-Azam and his Vision for Pakistan', page 60)

The unit 10 of STB Jamshoro class IX English textbook is titled '*Quaid-i-Azam and his Vision for Pakistan*'. The unit is full themes of freedom, equality, social justice and peaceful mutual co-existence. Through the device of '*intertextuality*', the author has embedded the message of equality by quoting directly from the text of speech contents of Mr. Jinnah the founder of Pakistan delivered to the first legislative assembly. The message of equal civil rights for all the citizens of newly formed State of Pakistan is prevalent in the text of speech-delivered by Mr. Jinnah. The extract has been quoted from the first speech of Mr. Muhammad Ali Jinnah addressed to the first Legislative Assembly of Pakistan as Governor General. The speech carries the message of equality of all citizens of Pakistan. The Quaid very clearly expressed that the newly created State was founded on the basis of two nation theory. However, after the creation of a nation state the identity based on various religions had no significance as all the citizens were Pakistani thereafter.

Textual Analysis of KTB Peshawar Extract

Hazrat Umar (RA) was so strict in the enforcement of impartial justice that he did not spare even his near and dear ones if were at fault. The history of the world cannot produce a single instance in which a state or public leader showed greater respect for justice and the rule of law. Hazrat Umar (RA) was kind and sympathetic to the needy. Unstinted service to humanity was his foremost concern. Honesty and integrity were the highest virtues in the character of the second caliph.

(KTB, X, Hazrat Umar Farooq (RA), page 83)

The unit 7 of KTB Peshawar class X English textbook is titled, '*Hazrat Umar Farooq (RA)*'. The index of the textbook has described the theme of the lesson as '*peaceful co-existence*'. Umar (RA) was the second caliph of Islamic caliphate. The author has enumerated the biographical account of the caliph in starting paragraph of the unit. Then the discourse of lesson focuses on simplicity and austerity displayed by the caliph in his personal and official capacities. The virtue of human and social equality has also been foregrounded in the unit. The selected extract from the unit attributes the ethics related theme of justice to the caliph. Justice demands neutrality and impartiality on the part of the person administering the role of a judge. Hazrat Umar (RA) was the embodiment of social justice and an exemplary judge of legal matters. He would decide all the cases brought before his court on merit rather than favouritism. The caliph vehemently abhorred nepotism. Once his real son committed some serious crime, and the case was tried in caliph's court. The real son of the caliph was awarded death penalty. Thus a classic example of justice was created by the caliph for future humanity. Even the non-Muslim historian would describe the second caliph of Islam as an embodiment of justice. The caliph was considerate and compassionate towards needy, destitute and poor subject of his State. He would disguise himself as a common man and roam in the streets to gather information about his state subjects. The author has foregrounded the virtues of humanism and sympathy present in the person of the caliph. As the discourse progresses the caliph has been attributed the virtues of honesty and integrity of Hazrat Umar (RA). Both the virtues are typical and prototype ethical qualities of a person. The young readership has been given an explicit and implicit message to follow and emulate the ethics-related behaviour of the second caliph of Islam.

Textual Analysis of PTB Lahore Extract

People can seek light from the message and guidance from his life to achieve perfection in the moral, spiritual and social areas of life..... An honest, fair and just business man. He advised the most equitable plan for the setting of the Black Stone.he decided all cases on merit with justice and equity, irrespective of color, creed, or race.The Jews, who were his bitter enemies, brought their suits to him and he decided cases in accordance with the Jewish law.He decided every case brought to him, by friend or foe with justice, without fear of favor.

(PTB, X, Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH) an Embodiment of Justice, page 4)

The unit 1 of class X English textbook is titled as '*Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH) an Embodiment of Justice*'. The lesson is having embedded themes of justice, social and racial equality. The Holy Prophet (PBUH) was spiritual leader of the Islamic State of Medina. The matters relating to Judiciary were also under his charter of duties. The lesson's textintensely focuses on moral aspects of the Holy Prophet (PBUH). Even before assuming the position of Islamic State leader, he was well known as an honest and truthful person. The attributes such as '*honest*', '*fair and just businessman*' have been foregrounded in the business deals of the Holy Prophet (PBUH). The personality traits described are purely of the time before assuming the leadership of Muslims.

The text describes that complete life of the Holy Prophet was full of self-examples of honesty and justice. A historic event has been narrated as argumentation tool, quoting that once there was a dispute between four tribes regarding the setting of Black Stone. Knowing the just traits of the Prophet, the tribal elders agreed upon referring the matter to him for arbitration. The Holy Prophet (PBUH) asked the four tribal chiefs to put the '*Black Stone*' on a four-cornered cloth, and four different tribal chiefs held each corner of the cloth. All the four tribes readily agreed to the plan of action suggested by the Holy Prophet (PBUH). The plan proposed by Holy Prophet was full of justice and wisdom. Thus, the imminent tribal dispute was averted through the amicable and just solution provided by the Holy Prophet (PBUH). The author further describes that while deciding the cases brought before him, the Holy Prophet (PBUH) would exercise total impartiality. He would remain above racial

discrimination. Even the influential people could not get undue favour from him. The Jews who were opposed to his teachings relating to faith would still have full trust in his impartiality. In case of any disputes between Jew families or persons the matter used to be brought before the Prophet (PBUH). He used to decide the cases with full equity and justice as per Jew laws. The Muslims have a strong belief in the words and actions of the Holy Prophet (PBUH). They draw inspiration from the life of Holy Prophet (PBUH). The ethics related traits like honesty and justice have been foregrounded by the author of the unit. The lesson is full of explicit and implicit messages for the young readership to emulate the honest and just actions of the Prophet (PBUH).

Readership Conceptions (Discourse Consumption)

The readership conceptions were obtained through the close ended questionnaire-based survey. Five-point Likert attitudinal scales were used for the purpose. The questionnaire was administered to 1560 female and male secondary level students of rural and urban areas of all the provinces of Pakistan. The relevant questions to human values or ethics were extracted from a larger PhD study questionnaire. An endeavor was made to gather the readership conceptions through indirect questions and drawing inferences. A board approved the content validity of questionnaire of research experts, whereas reliability was measured by entering the quantitative data in SPSS. The number of respondents and percentage of their responses are tabulated in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Readership Conceptions on Human Values

Question Statement	Publishing Board	Responses		
		%A	%DA	%DK
1. Patience is a commonly found quality in my class fellows.	BTB Quetta	20	65	15
	STB Jamshoro	35	60	5
	KTB Peshawar	18	73	9
	PTB Lahore	41	51	8
2. My fellows always show honesty in examinations.	BTB Quetta	10	85	5
	STB Jamshoro	8	83	9
	KTB Peshawar	14	80	6
	PTB Lahore	20	76	4
3. We should help non-Muslim poor People.	BTB Quetta	61	30	9
	STB Jamshoro	76	20	4
	KTB Peshawar	60	37	3
	PTB Lahore	71	25	4
4. Muslim and non-Muslim Pakistani citizens should have equal rights.	BTB Quetta	15	80	5
	STB Jamshoro	28	70	2
	KTB Peshawar	35	60	5
	PTB Lahore	40	51	9
5. My class fellows are full of humanism values.	BTB Quetta	55	40	5
	STB Jamshoro	67	30	3
	KTB Peshawar	71	27	3
	PTB Lahore	74	24	2

Note. Number of student respondents: Baluchistan 800, Sindh 650, KPK 925, Punjab/AJK/GB 2200, Total 4575
Key, A= Agree, DA= Disagree, DK = Don't Know, % = percentage, All values are reported as percentage for ease of comprehension.

Figure 1. Publishing board wise percentage of readership

Figure 2. Responses to 'Patience is a commonly found quality in my class fellows'

Figure 3. My fellows always show honesty in examinations

Figure 4. We should help non-Muslim poor People

Figure 5. Responses to 'Muslim and non-Muslim Pakistani citizens should have equal rights'

Figure 6. Responses to 'My class fellows are full of humanism values'

4.5 Curriculum and Syllabi Alignment

It is very pertinent to mention that at present 'National Curriculum-2006' has been fully implemented by Federal Government of Pakistan. The English Language Curriculum suggests certain themes such as bravery, honesty, fair play, truthfulness, friendship, tolerance, justice, patience, humanism, respect for elders, social adjustment, peaceful co-existence and gender equality as a guideline for provincial textbook developers for inclusion in secondary level syllabus books. The deeper and careful study and analysis of ELT textbooks' discourse of all the publishing boards is sufficiently containing the above referred themes and teachings about human values. The precise description of the key values has been given in table 1 above.

Findings and Discussion

The purpose of this study was to deconstruct human values embedded in secondary level ELT textbooks' discourse, gauge the alignment between curriculum and textbooks' themes pertaining to human values and to measure readerships' conceptions. The books published by all the provincial textbook boards were selected for analysis. The results indicated that the textbooks' contents were reasonably replete with themes of human

values as noted in table 1. All the publishing boards were found to focus on human values laden contents as directed by national curriculum 2006. The findings of this study endorsed the results of previous studies such as (Pinkley 2012) and (Baig et al 2020). The themes related to human values of ELT textbooks of four publishing boards vary in quality and quantity to a limited extent. Most of the themes of four sets of textbooks fairly resemble to each other. Another objective of this study was to gauge the readership conceptions pertaining to human values of four sets of ELT textbooks. A questionnaire-based survey was conducted in all four provinces of Pakistan. The quantitative results indicated that the values related to humanism and equality was opined to be in sufficient magnitude by the respondents whereas honesty and tolerance were agreed to by a small percentage of respondents. Study population of survey was male and female young readership of all the provinces of Pakistan. The sample of about fifteen hundred respondents is not thought to be sufficient to ensure the validity and reliability of findings of study. It is very likely that parental and social grooming plays very significant role in prospering ethics, morality and other humanism values in a society. Curriculum seems to play a small part towards such values. Moreover, socio cultural environments and religious practices seem to have their part in grooming of young readership. The table 2 and graphs reveal that readership of various provinces responds in a different way to particular survey questions. The literature review suggests that there is hardly any study previously carried out on the topic with such a wide settings. Moreover, only ELT textbooks have been targeted in this research whereas other social sciences have not been considered in this study. The generalizability of the study findings needs some more work in this area. Moreover, the findings of study also revealed that the students were not adequately able to recognize and practice human values and qualities such as tolerance, equality, humanism, patience, equity, justice, honesty, empathy which were thought significant in the curriculum for peaceful coexistence between persons, groups, societies and nations.

Conclusion

This research targeted the themes pertaining to human values such as honesty, justice, tolerance and patience embedded in discourse of ELT textbooks of four publishing boards of Pakistan, the alignment of curriculum with syllabus books and readership conceptions about human values. The study was conducted in two phases. In first part, textbooks' contents about human values were identified through intensive reading, the representative data were selected for analysis and critical discourse analysis of sample text was carried out by using Fairclough's (1995) three dimensional model of analysis and Van dijk's (2006) socio cultural approach. The second part of study gathered the young readership's conceptions through a questionnaire-base survey from all provinces of Pakistan. The study relied mainly on qualitative research method. The findings revealed that textbooks' discourse of all the publishing boards was reasonably having human values related themes such as honesty, patience and tolerance. The syllabus books' contents pertaining to human values were found adequately aligned with national curriculum 2006. The respondents of survey study displayed mixed trends towards conceptions pertaining to human values. On a comparative basis, Sindh Textbook Board (STB) Jamshoro readership displayed much improved attitude towards human values. This finding is suggestive of positive influence of textbook contents of mindset and attitude of readership.

Recommendations

The adequate inclusion of themes related to human values in ELT textbooks can make the readership appreciate worth and benefits of human values. An intensive study of all the textbooks of English, Islamic studies and other social sciences subjects should be conducted in all provinces of Pakistan for the purpose of evaluating the nature of human values related themes and their impact on young readership. Thereafter, textbook developers can included the deficient contents during revision process of various syllabus books.

References

- Ahmed, M., & Shah, S.K. (2014). The Relationship between Culture and ELT: The Representation of Aesthetic Sense Culture in "Oxford Progressive English". *Journal of Literature, Languages and Linguistics*, 4, 35-42.
- Al-Tamimi, A., & Shuib, M. (2009). Motivation and attitudes towards learning English: A study of petroleum engineering undergraduates at Hadhramout University of Sciences and Technology. *GEMA Online® Journal of Language Studies*, 9(2).
- Apple, M. W. (2004). *Ideology and Curriculum*. Rutledge.
- Ariyanti. (2016). MORAL VALUES IN EDUCATION: TEACHING ENGLISH CLASSROOM AT MA'HAD TAHFIZUL QUR'AN RAHMATULLAH SAMARINDA. *Script Journal: Journal of Linguistic and English Teaching*. 1. 11. 10.24903/sj.v1i1.14.
- Brown, G. (2004) Mapping Spatial Attributes in Survey Research for Natural Resource Management: Methods and Applications, *Society & Natural Resources*, 18:1, 17-39, DOI: 10.1080/08941920590881853
- Dornyei, Z. (2007) *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*. Oxford University Press.
- Fairclough, N. (1995). *Critical discourse analysis: The critical study of language*. Routledge.

- Galbraith, J.K. (2003) A History of Economics, Hamesh Hamilton London.
- Kress and Van Leeuwen's (1996). Reading Images, Routledge, Taylor& Francis Group, London and New York.
- Khattak, Z.et al (2011). An Investigation into the Causes of English Language Learning Anxiety in Students at AWKUM. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. 15. 1600-1604.10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.03.337.
- Maghsoudi, M. (2020). Comparing Representations of 'Self' and "Other" in Iranian and Indian English School Books: A Critical Discourse Analysis.
- Milton, J. (1644). Areopagitica, A Speech of Mr. John Milton for the Liberty of Unlicenc'd Printing to the Parliament of England (1 ed.). London.
- Nayyar, A. H., & Salim, A. (2005). The subtle subversion: The State of curricula and textbooks in Pakistan Urdu, English, Social Studies and Civics. Sustainable Development Policy Institute.
- inkley, D. (2012), Children Learning English as a Foreign Language, Pearson: Longman.
- Prabhu (2011). Human values in education: Reflecting on the core AMA International University of Bahrain
- Rass, R. (2014). Integrating Human Values in EFL Instruction. International Journal of English Language Education. 2. 62. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijele.v2i2.5814>
- Srinivasulu. B (2018). Human Values Through English Language Acquisition, Pune Research, An International Journal I English, Volume 4 , Issue 4. .
- Van Dijk, T. A. (2006). Discourse, context and cognition. Discourse Studies, 8(1), 159–177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461445606059565>
- Yaqoob, M. T. (2011). Ideology and worldview in textbooks: A study of cultural aspects in ELT in Pakistan. Doctoral dissertation, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan.
- Lombardi, D. (2013). Critical Discourse Analysis of online News Headlines: A Case of the Stoneman Douglas High School Shooting. Malmö University.

Author Information

Dr. Sajid Waqar (corresponding author)
Assistant Professor, Department of English,
University of Sialkot, Pakistan

Zarnab Ahmed
PhD Scholar, Department of English Linguistics,
The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan

Sania Jabeen
Ph.d Scholar, Department of English Linguistics,
The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan.
